

Anion-exchange Selectivity of ClO_4^- , CNS^- , I^- and NO_3^- on Dowex I-X8 (Cl) in Water-2-Methoxyethanol Mixed Media

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The exchange study of ClO_4^- , CNS^- , I^- and NO_3^- against Cl^- on Dowex I-X8 in water-2-methoxyethanol of varying compositions at 303 ± 1 K was carried out. The selectivity decreased with increase in 2-methoxyethanol. The selectivity sequence in aqueous medium is $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{CNS}^- > \text{I}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^-$. The sequence changes to $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{I}^- > \text{CNS}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^-$ in mixed media.

Many organic solvents with varied solvent properties such as protic and aprotic nature, dielectric constant, dipole moment, etc. have been used to study the behaviour of ion-exchange selectivity in mixed solvent systems¹. 2-Methoxyethanol, a substituted alcohol, has been used for the first time in the exchange study of anions such as ClO_4^- , CNS^- , I^- and NO_3^- against Cl^- on strong base resin Dowex I-X8.

Results and Discussion

For an ion-exchange reaction,

the rational thermodynamic constant $K_a^{\text{B}^-}$ in both aqueous and mixed solvent medium is represented by the equation²⁻⁴,

$$\log K_a^{\text{B}^-} = \int_0^1 \log K_o^{\text{B}^-} - dN_{\text{RB}} + 2 \log \frac{f_{\pm \text{XA}}}{f_{\pm \text{XB}}} + \log Q = \log K_{aA}^{\text{B}^-} + \log Q' \quad (2)$$

where,

$$K_{aA}^{\text{B}^-} = \frac{m_A^- N_{\text{RB}}}{m_B^- N_{\text{RA}}}$$

where m_A and m_B are the solution phase molalities and N_{RA} and N_{RB} the resin phase mole fractions. For $f_{\pm \text{XA}}/f_{\pm \text{XB}}$, the ratio of activity coefficient of the two counter ions in 2-methoxyethanol-water medium, the one in aqueous medium is used as per Harned's second rule⁵. Q' includes solvent activity terms and the activity coefficient corrections for the differences in the standard states of the resin and the external solution phase^{4,5}. Due to paucity of data, the value of Q' is not evaluated. Hence averaged and corrected selectivity coefficient $\log K_a^{\text{B}^-}$ in 2-methoxyethanol-water mixed medium thus computed are summarised in Table 1.

The order of selectivity in aqueous medium is $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{CNS}^- > \text{I}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^-$. This is the order expected from their crystallographic radii and the

data in literature⁷ and also in agreement with the reported models^{8,9}.

TABLE 1—AVERAGED AND CORRECTED SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENTS WITH 2-METHOXYETHANOL CONCENTRATION

2-Methoxy-ethanol (% w/w)	$\text{ClO}_4^-/\text{Cl}^-$	CNS^-/Cl^-	I^-/Cl^-	$\text{NO}_3^-/\text{Cl}^-$
0	1.56	1.50	1.38	0.59
20	1.32	1.17	1.22	0.48
40	1.25	0.80	0.97	0.40
60	0.98	0.35	0.73	0.23
80	0.56	0.10	0.60	0.12

Qualitatively the same selectivity order was obtained by free energy data (Table 2). According to the Diamond and Whitney⁸, the bigger monovalent anion such as ClO_4^- tends to tighten up water structure surrounding them in the same way as do hydrophobic molecules, thus reducing the entropy of the system. The large quaternary ammonium group in the resin in contact with solution has already resulted in decrease in entropy. In order to avoid further decrease in entropy, ClO_4^- is forced to the same cavity created by quaternary ammonium group. This water-structure enforced ion-pairing explains the higher selectivity of bigger anions. According to Reichenberg⁹ also the smaller ion with more negative hydration free energy goes to the external solution phase. It can be seen that Diamond's⁸ water structure enforced ion-pairing and Reichenberg's⁹ hydration free energy concepts are complementary to each other.

TABLE 2

Anion	Radius (Crystallographic) in Å	Hydration free energy $\Delta G_{i(h)}$ in kJ mole^{-1}
ClO_4^-	2.9	209.20
CNS^-	-	230.12 ^a
I^-	2.20	267.77
NO_3^-	2.0—2.5	288.69

^a Estimated.

There is decrease in the selectivity coefficient for all the ion-pairs studied with the increase in 2-methoxyethanol content. However, there is crossover of selectivity between CNS^- — Cl^- and I^- — Cl^- in mixed medium at about 20% where the order becomes, $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{I}^- > \text{CNS}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^-$ (Fig. 1). The steep reduction in selectivity of ClO_4^- , I^- and CNS^- may be attributed to rapid destruction of water-structure with the addition of the solvent. In the case of NO_3^- , change in the water-structure is gradual and therefore the reduction in selectivity is less rapid.

Fig. 1. $\log K_{a,Cl}^{B-}$ vs 2-methoxyethanol (% w/w) on Dowex 1-X8, (■) ClO_4^- , (▲) CNS^- , (○) I^- and (●) NO_3^- .

Athavale *et al.*¹⁰ in their cation-exchange studies on strong and weak acid cation-exchangers have reported change in the order of affinities from $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{NH}_4^+ < \text{K}^+$ in aqueous medium to $\text{Li}^+ < \text{NH}_4^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+$ in mixed solvent medium. Bhat¹¹ reported similar crossover between CNS^- and I^- in water-methanol mixed medium. Athavale *et al.*¹⁰ attributed this behaviour of NH_4^+ to its non-spherical nature, and perhaps to swollen volume of NH_4^+ form of resin being higher than that of Na^+ . The anomalous behaviour of CNS^- in the mixed medium in the present investigation may therefore be attributed to non-spherical nature of CNS^- . Further, greater interaction between CNS^- and 2-methoxyethanol (ion-solvent) in organic solvent rich medium in the external phase may also contribute significantly to crossover behaviour of CNS^- and I^- .

Experimental

All reagents used were of A.R. grade. 2-Methoxyethanol was dried (anhydrous K_2CO_3) followed by fractionation.

Ion-exchange resin: Dowex 1-X8 (50–100 mesh; Fluka) was conditioned by treatment in a column of conventional design with 0.5M NaOH (free from carbonate) and 0.5M HCl alternately. Finally it was converted into the chloride form, washed with double-distilled water till the washings were free from chloride and air-dried. In order to determine the capacity the resin (1 g) was shaken with a known volume (40 cm³) of 2M KNO_3 at 303 ± 1 K for ~4 h. Displaced chloride was determined volumetrically by Volhard's method. Concentration of the counter ion (Cl^-) was calculated to be 2.9810 meq per g of the resin. The resin (1 g) was heated at 333 ± 1 K in an oven for about 12 h, then in a vacuum oven to constant weight and the moisture content was calculated to be 20.27%.

Determination of selectivity coefficient: Equilibrium studies were carried out with the resin (0.250 g) and electrolyte solutions of exchanging counter ions of 0.05M in different proportions to give a total volume of 30 cm³. For the exchange study in mixed medium, electrolyte solutions prepared in 20, 40, 60 and 80% (w/w) of 2-methoxyethanol were taken. Batches were equilibrated by shaking for 16 h. The external solution phase was then analysed for the estimation of counterions by suitable volumetric methods. In the case of NO_3^- — Cl^- and ClO_4^- — Cl^- systems, the chloride content of the solution was estimated by Volhard's method. In the I^- — Cl^- and CNS^- — Cl^- systems, the exchanging anions I^- and CNS^- were determined by titrating with standard potassium iodate solution. These data, together with the previously determined capacity of the resin, were used to evaluate the selectivity coefficient, K_{CA}^{B-} values for each loading.

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